

How to Break Down Barriers to Learning Languages of Europe

Bullet points and statements

2025

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What's this?

A collection of lifehacks. Or just call them observations.

Lifehacks are everywhere. How yours are special?

- Mine are repurposed from Conference Interpreting and Translation.
- I tested mine on myself, I shared them with my students, and the whole thing worked.
- I checked with the latest advances in educational sciences.

Who is your audience?

- Some tutors who teach languages of Europe.
- Some translators and Interpreters who are taking another C language on board.
- Some independent learners who want to explore a different approach.

Who is NOT your audience?

- Tutors hoping for a free database of magical advice.
- Entrepreneurs looking for a startup idea.
- Learners hoping for a quick fix with their homework.

So what *is* this then??

A self-help guide for some people who feel uncomfortable learning / teaching a foreign language.

- If you feel like you don't know where to start or how to proceed;
- if you feel stuck at some point; or
- if your current learning feels different from your usual experience –

those may be the signs of the teaching practices that do not fit your profile. I can help you figure out what exactly may be going wrong. It will then be up to you to look for an alternative in your immediate environment.

What languages are exemplified here?

English and Finnish.

Table of Contents

About the author	3
About the approach offered in this booklet	4
A special learning profile	4
The Five component model	5
An example from the Finnish language	6
Individual components	13
Words	13
Effect of Words on listeners	14
Slots	15
Effect of Slots on listeners	16
Connections	17
Effect of Connections on listeners	18
Combinations	19
Effect of Combinations on listeners	20
Patterns	21
Effect of Patterns on listeners	23
Practical uses	24
To track individual progress	24
Summary	24
Skills by category	25
To teach English	28
Introductory note	28
Common roles of ‘-ing’ words	31
Nominalization	32
Participles and Adjectives	33
The tricky ‘to’	34
Rules of good text	36
A few practical examples (from my former blog)	37
Teaching Finnish to Immigrants in Finland: Firsthand Account of a Language Professional	37
Is Finnish taught to immigrants properly?	37
What makes the teaching methods old-school?	37
A classroom is a mix of epistemic profiles	37
Why profiles remain overlooked?	38
‘Too much, too busy, too complicated, and therefore not feasible and none of my business’. What can be done?	38
Learn from CELTA and assign emotional values	39
Virheellinen Sliders	39
Subject-specific lessons for A2 level learners	40
A Conversation with a Talented Learner	42

About the author

A freelance translator / terminologist with experience at International Organizations and a CELTA-certified teacher of English. Passionate about bridging gaps in professional communication.

- **I have a successful track-record of a total of six years at various agencies of the UN as a translator and terminologist.** My duties included: *data collection, literature search, document screening, reference management, project management, localization of documentation, development of reference materials, cooperation in an international team of professionals.*
 - **I have about thirteen years' experience as a freelance simultaneous interpreter in the free market.** I worked in a wide range of sectors, from sports to veterinary education. In this role, I successfully *solved ad-hoc problems, organized team work, managed client communications and handled day-to-day business practicalities, as well as provided guidance to junior colleagues.*
 - **I am a CELTA-certified teacher of English with experience in the academia.** Since 2012, I have taken part in *teaching, developing custom-made learning products, organizing educational events for post-degree professionals, and adapting the existing instructional materials to learners' needs.*
 - **I have formal degrees in Medicine, Education, and Conference Interpreting as well as certification in Advanced Methods in Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses.** I believe in continuing professional development, and I regularly take formal courses at recognized educational institutions to stay honed. I believe that my current blend of skills and experience is truly interdisciplinary and transferable. **My dream is to repurpose some approaches from public health for teaching languages.**
-

About the approach offered in this booklet

A special learning profile

Our learning behaviours can be traced back to a few common profiles. That's what the recent studies in educational psychology indicate.

Likewise, our language learning behaviours can be attributed to a few common profiles. That's what the studies in communication reveal.

Proper language learning just takes the right approach. It shouldn't be too painful or too difficult.

Yet, innovative methods often seem to be left outside the usual practices for very long.

This is probably one of the reasons why learning a foreign language is still considered to be intrinsically hard and unrewarding by a large number of people, including, teachers themselves.

I've met a lot of language learners who have shaped their own mindset for learning. They don't necessarily know what type of profile they are.

What they know is that the learning they are offered often falls short of their expectations. They believe that any piece of the newly acquired knowledge should be integrated into what they already know.

They often feel the need to build at least a few important links between what they have learned in the past and what they have got to know recently. This type of learner has a name. It is a Knowledge Builder.

At least some of them may also perceive a foreign language in a very special way. To them, it is a part of their identity. A recent Finnish study calls them *pidättäytyvä perfektionisti* (~ 'a cautious perfectionist'), although this name might not be entirely fitting.

What these individuals need throughout their learning path is a fail-safe environment. They don't usually improvise. They carefully plan first and check how it works out later.

Do not assume they are shy. Do not encourage them to 'take it easy'. A foreign language is their identity. They mean to keep it authentic, however recently they may have started their studies. What they also need is a predictable learning setup.

If it sounds like someone you know of (yourself included), this booklet would benefit you most.

If you are a 'cautious perfectionist', I'm sure you will be happy to explore the Five components. If you seek to offer help to a 'cautious perfectionist', you will find out what they likely need most.

And if either of you wants to keep track of the progress, I believe the Five components is the way to go.

Finally, I validated this model for interpreter training and tested it on myself when I learned Finnish. This could give you some ideas about its practical usage.

The Five component model

The graphics below tells you what happens when you speak a foreign language. This is a simplified illustration of the core principles of the Interpretive Theory of Translation.

Focus on how you feel when you speak. Focus on how you feel when you hear someone else speak.

This approach receives a lot of attention in interpreter training, but gets almost zero attention in language learning. I think it doesn't have to be like that.

The greatest strength of this theory is that it very precisely maps your strengths and weaknesses when you translate. And it actually comes in handy when you speak a foreign language. Some people may say that this theory is outdated. However, it still remains a valid teaching model for training interpreters at the top level.

Figure 1. How communication happens

Before your message can get through, you and your listeners have to take three important steps. There is a whole bunch of things that can go wrong at any given step. However, if you know the key components of every step, you can easily manage the communication process. The Interpretive Theory of Translation talks about the three stages of communication. Meanwhile, the Five components are not in the original version of the theory.

The *Symbols* section describes each of the individual components: what they are, why they are important, what problems they lead to, what benefits they bring, and, most importantly, how do you know whether a specific component works for you or not.

An example from the Finnish language

Figure 2. The Five Component model that you are probably using already

Basic Things to remember with Finnish nouns

SOUNDS

- a. Consonant gradation ('KPT')
- b. Vowel changes (e.g. 'huone - huoneessa')

CASES

Commonly used cases
(*'kieliopilliset
sijamuodot'*)

- 1. nominatiivi
- 2. genetiivi
- 3. partitiivi
- 4. akkusatiivi

Locative cases

Internal
(*'sisäpaikallissijat'*)

- 5. inessiivi
- 6. elatiivi
- 7. illatiivi

External
(*'ulkopaikallissijat'*)

- 8. adessiivi
- 9. ablatiivi
- 10. allatiivi

Other cases (*'muut
sijamuodot'*)

- 11. essiivi
- 12. translatiivi
- 13. abessiivi
- 14. instruktiivi
- 15. komitatiivi

Figure 3. Basics to remember with a Finnish noun. Circular chart

Basic Things to remember with Finnish verbs

SOUNDS

a. Consonant gradation (depends on Verb types)

TENSES

1. Past
2. Present
3. Future

MOODS

4. Indicative
5. Imperative
6. Conditional

TRANSITIVITY

7. Intransitive verbs
8. Monotransitive verbs
9. Ditransitive verbs

The two below certainly can't be called 'Transitivity'; place here out of convenience

10. Existential (such as 'olla')
11. Other existential verbs (such as 'tulla', e.g. 'ilma tulee kuumaksi')

SPECIAL REQUIREMENTS FOR REKTIO

12. Verb may be listed in *Tarkista tästä* or a similar reference as requiring a special case of Noun (e.g. the famous 'tykkään kahvista')

Figure 4. Basics to remember with a Finnish verb. Circular chart

What will it take to
build a sentence?

First, just a bunch of Words

Figure 5. Component one: Words

Next, a 'vector' of the situation

(yes, as in 'vector database')

*(these are 8 most common sentence types,
e.g. check Fred Karlsson's
Comprehensive Grammar of Finnish)*

Figure 6. Vector of the situation that will define further components, primarily Slots (Component two)

'Vectors' define sequence of Words
and also their Connections

Figure 7. Component three: Connections

And finally,
you check for better alternatives to Combinations
or maybe even the whole phrase, who knows!

Figure 8. Components four and five: Combinations and Patterns

Individual components

Words

What is this?

Perhaps, one of the most obvious things that we associate with learning languages. And something that many of us probably blame for the insufficient mastery of a foreign language.

However, we often attribute to words the issues that are actually caused by Combinations.

If you are often misunderstood, chances are that learning more words may not help. In fact, you may want to explore the probable combinations of the words of your vocabulary relatively early on during your learning.

Why this is important?

We probably give too much attention to the pure collection of words (may I even say hoarding). But then a common problem comes. If you look through your lists of words, you will probably notice that:

- (a) there are duplicates all over (i.e. you've repeatedly jotted down many words over the previous 4 – 5 months, and each repetition occurs at least two or three times); and
- (b) a fair share of your notes doesn't look very familiar.

I've heard all sorts of things to explain this observation: poor memory, lack of time, **and even the intense self-criticism about not being diligent**. But anyway, words seem to get memorized (and forgotten, too) at their own pace.

So why simply pile up more and more new lists? Focus on how words interact with each other to produce a relatively clear and unambiguous sentence. Is it not what we actually aim for in our learning?

Whose pain it is?

Words are listener's and speaker's pain alike. As a language learner, you may know this feeling of being stuck with lengthy dictionary search before saying anything. You may also know this feeling when, despite all efforts, the listener is still struggling to grasp the meaning.

Conversely, the super good knowledge of words will make people say that you have broad vocabulary. On many occasions, however, you will likely feel that the vast vocabulary itself just doesn't help.

Effect of Words on listeners

Figure 9. Effects that your high (top left) or low (top right) mastery of **Words** likely produces on your listeners (bottom left and bottom right respectively)

Slots

What is this?

'Slot' is a simple word that I use to refer to something that has the official name of 'syntactic roles'.

'Slots' is much better, isn't it? If you compare a sentence to a bookshelf (or maybe a rack of shelves), then places for individual words are Slots.

When someone refers to the 'word order', this is actually one more example of Slots.

Why this is important?

You normally don't notice Slots (or rather, they don't bother too much), until the learner has tried to build a really specific phrase that addresses a particular aspect of some situation.

Compare Finnish and English:

'Sitä haluan sanoa' – 'This is what I want to say'.

In grammar books, this is often described as the sentence types.

My empirical observations seem to suggest that the quickest way to understand

(a) sentence types;

(b) the way they are built; and

(c) the ideas that they convey **is visual diagrams**.

A Slot is the main element of such diagrams. Probably the greatest value of Slots is that they can tell you, how much effort is needed to express a specific idea in a specific language.

Whose pain it is?

It is everyone's pain, but no one seems to know that.

Interpreters and grammarians work a lot at the Slots level, so Slots are thought to be either too specialized or too academic a problem. Yet, they're not.

It becomes learner's pain, if they wanted to express themselves unambiguously and make really precise statements. Borrowing from the mother tongue may not help at all and be counterproductive.

It is listener's pain. If you listen to a language learner, sometimes you may not even guess that they are copying structures from their mother tongue. You may try to link what you hear to the closest similar phrase in your language and totally misunderstand the learner.

It is teacher's pain. Sentence types, their components, and the ideas that they convey generally seem to be left out of language teaching. However, I saw various teaching resources on the web that take care of this problem, and they seem to be popular with the learners.

Effect of Slots on listeners

Figure 10. Effects that your high (top left) or low (top right) mastery of Slots likely produces on your listeners (bottom left and bottom right respectively)

Connections

Summary

We seem to assume that a sentence is a 100% blank page that we can freely fill in with whatever we want. In fact, language is a set of ready-made forms or templates, in which you only fill the gaps.

The traditional approach to learning languages is that you start with words, preferably those that denote familiar things (such as a cup, a plate, a wall, etc.). Then you go on with modifications, e.g. plurals (cups, plates, walls, etc.). After that you probably go on with referring to the familiar things (e.g., this is a cup, these are cups, etc.). Most likely, you are hardly ever explicitly told about the templates.

When was the last time anyone explicitly told you that every sentence has places for individual words? Did they tell you the number of words was limited? Seriously. I mean, a sentence can have unlimited word count only in theory. In reality, we are using reasonably long sentences, aren't we?

For example, one of the rules of thumb in spoken English is to use sentences between 9 – 12 words long. You are perfectly entitled to writing a 35 – 40 words sentence, provided it is really clear and straightforward. Is this not a template?

Words are generally not allowed to take places in a sentence randomly. There are only about 8 – 10 basic sentence types, and they have a clearly determined arrangement of words. This refers to English and Finnish alike.

These sentence types denote a few basic ideas, such as *who has what, who does what, what happens when*, etc. It is within this framework that you actually build all your sentences.

In this booklet, I use the word 'Slots'. *It means a group of one-word spaces (or gaps) that can take about 8 basic configurations and express a few basic ideas.* Not all Words are randomly allowed into any Slots. Quite often Slots are designed for specific Words solely.

This section is about **Connections**. They are **modifications that you make to Words so that they become fit for specific Slots**. For example, unless you add '-lla', there is no way to say 'I have a car' – 'Minulla on auto'. In English, it is literally a connection: you embark *at* a ship, but embark *on* a new project. In this '*who-does-what*' template 'at' or 'on' literally makes the last slot suitable/unsuitable for 'ship' or 'project'.

Effect of Connections on listeners

Figure 11. Effects that your high (top left) or low (top right) mastery of **Connections** likely produces on your listeners (bottom left and bottom right respectively)

Combinations

What is this?

Short pieces, such as pairs and threes of words, that native speakers would call ‘correct’, ‘natural’, ‘common’, ‘typical’, etc.

If you listen carefully to native speakers, you will quickly notice such pairs and threes of words. For example: ‘pitää itsestäänselvyytenä’, ‘tehdä asioita loppuun’, ‘tilapäinen sopimus’, etc.

Why this is important?

First, combinations are different across languages. If I wanted to tell you about a list of problems 1 – 5, although the *Idea* were the same, I’d say “Minä menen järjestyksessä” in Finnish, whereas in English I’d say something like “I’ll go through each item as listed,” or “I’ll go through each item one-by-one.”

Second, combinations are not always addressed in dictionaries, because they are not individual words.

Some people would say that you can combine words freely in a language, so can you realistically make a list of all combinations in the first place? Actually, they are not as free as it seems. You can have ‘tilapäinen sopimus’ and ‘tilapäinen suhde’. But how about ‘tilapäinen päätös’ or ‘tilapäinen nimitys’? Would you not prefer ‘väliaikainen’ instead?

Looks like some combinations are just better.

Whose pain it is?

It seems to be mostly the reader’s / listener’s pain.

As a native speaker, you actually expect the learner to use a specific combination. Imagine, I said “Minä puhun näistä ongelmista, tällä tavalla, millä ne ovat lueteltu” 😊 or “Minä puhun näistä ongelmista toinen toisensa peräkkäin.”

You probably would guess the meaning of the last one, but you would probably ask yourself “Why wouldn’t he just put it more simply? Does he actually mean ‘järjestyksessä’?” Well... truth is, I sometimes cannot put it any better, because I don’t know the right Combination. So I just end up *copying* from a different language that I know well.

Apparently, many learners are unaware of the scale of this problem and are fine with that. While Combinations are addressed by courses in Interpretation and Translation or Academic Writing, they seem to be underemphasized (seriously overlooked) in language learning.

Effect of Combinations on listeners

Figure 12. Effects that your high (top left) or low (top right) mastery of **Combinations** likely produces on your listeners (bottom left and bottom right respectively)

Patterns

What is this?

In the context of this booklet, Patterns are stock phrases of three words or longer, such as ‘toistaiseksi voimassa oleva’. They are often referred to as *functional language* elsewhere.

This booklet calls shorter phrases *Combinations*, with the exception of two-word proverbs, such as ‘aikaa lentaa’, and fixed phrases, such as ‘miten voit’. Unlike the true Combinations, you cannot change the proverbs and fixed expressions, if you want them to remain understandable. Thus, the two-word proverbs and fixed phrases also count as Patterns.

Why this is important?

Patterns are important because they speed up communication. And indeed clarify it. A body of research from different domains of knowledge has shown that people do not rely on complicated logic in their daily lives but prefer shortcuts instead. The same is relevant for numerical data. Even experts in Public Health have been shown to prefer simplified verbal gists over numerical data. This was one of the reasons to introduce Plain Language Summaries to GRADE SoF tables.

Can you think of easier or more elegant alternatives to ‘how old are you?’, ‘every other day’, or ‘until proven otherwise’. Well, one could probably come up with something else, but will it sound equally clear? Patterns is one more component that, if misused by the learner, probably makes the native listener feel **slightly annoyed**. **If, indeed, there is a straightforward and easy way to put it, why on Earth it is framed that awkwardly?**

For example, if I speak decent English, you will assume that ‘I owe it all to you’ is a relatively familiar phrase to me. I mean, there is no way for you to figure out how much of English I really know, and how *uneven* my knowledge is. Then I intend to thank you for your contribution in some enterprise and say ‘This all happened because of what you had done before’. Meaning, ‘I owe it all to you’. Well, if I can handle Past Perfect (*I said ‘had done’, this probably tells you that I may be familiar with a bit of grammar*), do I actually *not* know ‘I owe it all to you’ (*kind of easier than the sequence of tenses*)? Am I being ironical? Or do I not know the correct phrase? Or am I making fun? Or could I really have *that* uneven level of English? Or am I just mocking everyone around?

As you have probably noticed, the misuse of any of the five components (Words-Slots-Connections-Combinations-Patterns) produces the feeling of discomfort in the listeners. **With Words, Patterns and Connections it is really strong, whereas with Slots and Combinations it is a bit weaker but still bothersome.** Thus, we could say that the components are ‘unspecific’. The feedback from listeners will be pretty much the same all the time: ‘I did not quite understand’. However, each of the components feels differently to the speaker. And that’s the key.

Interpreters know it all too well. During the training, they often get a uniform type of feedback: ‘not quite clear’, ‘did not quite understand’, ‘(s)he does not really translate super well’. In order to make feedback meaningful, it is important to keep track of all the five components in your own speech and observe how people react to the modifications. For example, you’ve improved your Slots component, and after that you’ve received softer feedback. If, however, you are pretty sure that Slots have improved, but the feedback has not, you could try to improve a different component.

Whose pain it is?

Patterns are primarily the learner's pain. They make learners feel shy and uncomfortable. **With the weak knowledge of Patterns, learners tend to limit their speaking to shorter sentences and simpler ideas.** Experiments with saying it all in one's own words often fail if there is a frequently used Pattern that conveys the same meaning. If you think about it for a moment, you will realize that there are frequently used Patterns for nearly every meaning. This is why interpreters actually pick up, learn and reproduce as much Patterns as they can rather than try to frame it all in their own words.

By the way, I have not calculated the number of Patterns in this booklet, but my recent indexing experiments have shown that it contains only **1500 unique English words**. This is probably another evidence to the fact that even a small repertoire of components can make your language workable.

Effect of Patterns on listeners

Figure 13. Effects that your high (top left) or low (top right) mastery of *Patterns* likely produces on your listeners (bottom left and bottom right respectively)

Practical uses

To track individual progress

Summary

From Regular Usage of English to Keskitason YKI-testi in 6 months.

Although my timid attempts to pick up some Finnish first started in 2018 or so, and despite two or three online courses, I did not even try to communicate with Finns in any other language than English.

An intense 6-months' course between November 2022 and May 2023 helped me develop enough confidence and skill to take keskitason YKI-testi in May 2023 and pass it with a solid B1 across all the four traditional domains of assessment (Listening, Speaking, Reading, Writing).

The course's environment produced a conducive atmosphere for asking myself, what I have learned, what I failed to learn, and why. This section provides a timeline of my skills between November 2022 and May 2023. It is based on my own self-observations and, certainly, is rooted in the theoretical framework that this booklet offers.

My golden standard was Northern Ostrobothnia Museum in Oulu. I went there on many occasions and tried to understand what the labels on the exhibits said. The collections of the museum reflect various aspects of daily life, plus the label texts are relatively formal. So I thought to myself that this is just right for the YKI-testi.

I thought that if I learn how to refer to objects and pictures, how to briefly describe what-happened-when, how to say 'A is probably related to B', **it will be a decent repertoire of things that I need for my test**. This repertoire is actually called specifications, and I deliberately relied on this framework to structure my learning and to explore as much components of the specifications as I could.

Skills by category

Words

November

I actively took note of useful techniques to build words. Back then I was pleasantly surprised by the words 'erityyppinen' and 'yksivärinen'.

I consciously realized¹ that eri-/yksi- + nen might be a good way to extend my vocabulary without actually learning too many new words.

May

By early May I already had a **vast collection of specific examples** that supported my guesses / added to the already existing lists. For example, finding the combination 'keittokuopan poikkileikkaus' in the museum felt extremely rewarding: by that time, I already knew the saying 'halki, poikki ja pinoon' (sort of 'over and done with'), and was able to guess that 'poikkileikkaus' meant 'cross-section'.

Slots

November

No changes over this period

Before the beginning of my studies, I made myself a **reference table** based on quality reference books. It covered the **sentence types, the word order and syntactic roles**. I looked into this table hundreds of times throughout the course, but it did not require any amendments over the 6 months. It was sufficiently helpful to get the Slots just right.

May

No changes over this period

Before the beginning of my studies, I made myself a **reference table** based on quality reference books. It covered the **sentence types, the word order and syntactic roles**. I looked into this table hundreds of times throughout the course, but it did not require any amendments over the 6 months. It was sufficiently helpful to get the Slots just right.

¹ I am using the words 'consciously realize' or 'internalize' synonymously. I think the best Finnish equivalent is 'sisältyä' or 'omistautua'. By this I mean that although the learner (i.e. me for that matter) might know a certain rule, they don't actively use it. A certain construction or word is not their first-tier solution, and they often spend a lot of time and effort to convey a specific meaning in a different (and often unnatural) way. My personal approach to internalizing rules or commonalities **is to take conscious note of them as much as I can**.

Connections

November

At first, I could not get used to cases, and, as **a temporary measure**, I started to deliberately overuse postpositives.

I collected all conceivable words that were real postpositives (such as 'jälkeen' or 'vieressä'), as well as adverbs and similar words, such as 'tarvittaessa' or 'suhteen'). This helped me build understandable phrases and not feel incapable of speaking. However, I admit that 'menen bussiin avulla' (I travel with the help of a bus) instead of 'bussilla' (by bus) is indeed weird.

May

By January my abuse of postpositives was over, and I felt relatively at ease with cases.

Of course, I don't claim to be 100% fine with the object cases (who would dare to?).

However, upon **reading** a bit of *Finnish: A Comprehensive Grammar* by **Fred Karlsson**, I started **to draw analogies with the English articles**, which has simplified my life a lot.

So when I saw 'kuvassa näkyy punaista, palanutta hiekkaa, palanutta kiveä ja hiiltä' in the museum, I felt I was perfectly fine with the Partitive. I think I am now consistently using it in similar situations.

Combinations

November

I was abusing the postpositives, and I knew it was uncommon. I realized that this kind of workaround would not always work. I tried **to pick up as much sample phrases** with postpositives as I could, so as to later **reproduce them in my own speech**. This is why finding a new combination, such as 'valjata ja nahkoja varten' felt like a small victory, because postpositives are indeed being used in moderation.

May

After I moved away from postpositives altogether, I was trying to focus on isolated combinations of words. Overall, it was a success, but **unless** these combinations are **frequently used**, they tend to be moved to the **passive memory**.

November

This booklet talks about Patterns. By this I mean stock phrases of three words or longer. They are often referred to as *functional language*.

I call shorter ones Combinations, with the exception of two-word proverbs, such as 'aikaa lentaa'. Unlike the true combinations, the proverbs are fixed expressions that you actually cannot change, if they were to remain understandable.

I incorporated combinations into my learning relatively early, because this is how I was trained as an interpreter, and I knew this would definitely help. Over the course of 3 months, there was no need for longer pieces of text. However, toward April I've realized that I've **somehow started to collect longer chunks**, such as Patterns.

May

Although the transition to Patterns had been subtle and went unnoticed, now I realize that I was giving them the greatest emphasis. I was in a desperate search of **reference constructions**, i.e. stock phrases that would help me convey some very important Ideas:

- when something happened;
- what condition / state something is in;
- how the condition has changed, if it has.

I was also looking for verbs with broad meanings (such as 'to get' or 'to bring' in English) that would give me a lot of flexibility. For example, 'pystyä', 'tulla', or 'käyttää'.

This is why the following phrases came into my notes:

- 'kanoja ei käytetty ravinnoksi, vaan niiden merkitys oli munantuotannossa' — a Pattern would be *Olla + käytetty + ...-ksi* (something is used for a specific purpose);
- 'alliomaalauskohtetta kalliuseinämissä maalina on käytetty punamultaa, johon on sekoitettu esimerkiksi rasvaa, pihkaa tai verta' — *...-na + olla + käytetty + ...* (something is used in a specific quality); or
- 'ne ovat saattaneet littyä kulttipaikkoihin' — an extremely useful Pattern meaning 'might have been related to'. Although we often say 'voisi olla' or 'voi olla', a more formal option seems to be 'saattaa olla', and I really liked that one.

In general, my approach to all of the components (from Words to Patterns) is **to collect specific examples that confirm the guesses rooted in my slowly evolving language intuition**.

I check with the people around me, how they would frame a specific meaning. A couple of examples would be 'I drop off the bus' ('jään') vs 'I leave my bag here' ('pidetään', although you could expect 'jätän'), or the preferable use of 'rupean' instead of 'aloitan' ('I begin'). One may object that either option is correct. However, I personally put significant emphasis on how people in my environment / frequently contacted places frame it.

To teach English

Introductory note

Implementing a simpler, Three-component model to teach English is briefly addressed in a few videos on my YouTube channel (https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLX_5SuFySLpu9GnKJmnAqZKESDSGei_P0).

I used to deliver a course in identifying grammar structures in academic texts (*GSI for Grammar Structure Identification*). The overall point was to teach students to quickly scan academic papers and ‘triage’ the pieces of grammar that they found challenging.

Quick triage requires a simplified model, which is exactly what this booklet offers. At GSI course, the model was even simpler. **It was a three-component model [repurposed from Interpreting and Translation](#).**

Figure 14. A simplified three-component model of the Sentence Structure

-
- ❖ The model is quite simple and practical. However, this comes at a cost: it sometimes deviates from the academic grammar.

This is true for phrases like “I am available” vs “I am obliged”.
From the academic grammar perspective, both cases are complex predicates. They are composed of an auxiliary component (“am”) plus the notional component (“available” or “obliged”, respectively). Although they are different subtypes of the complex predicate, and have different functions (e.g. “I’m obliged” is a passive form), they are still considered one entity. So academic grammar would say that these sentences are two-component: Subject (“I”) plus Predicate containing several elements (“am available” or “am obliged”).

- ❖ This would not be practical in note-taking. Interpreters work with large chunks or clusters of information. They focus and convey in their translation the following (among other):

- *Did A do anything? or Did anything happen to A? (i.e. Active voice vs Passive voice);*
- *Is this a fact or an opinion? (i.e. what the modality of this information is);*
- *Does the speaker project any attitude? (e.g. through the usage of modifiers).*

This is why “I’m available” vs “I’m obliged” would be seen differently.
The first is active and originates from the speaker. The speaker will actively share their availability with you if you ask them.
Whereas the second is passive and is probably imposed on the speaker against their will. They probably don’t want to, but still they are under an obligation.
This makes a difference for interpretation.

For this reason “I am available” is seen as [Agent] [=] [Adjective]. Note that there is no Recipient because “am” is used as the *link verb*. i.e. the sentence is about the Agent being something or someone.

-
- ❖ In principle *[Agent] [=] [Adjective]* may seem true for “I am obliged”. You may remember from the refresher on Participles (comes below) that they are often used as Adjectives in a sentence. However, this is a passive construction, so “I” is Recipient, not Agent.

 - ❖ Passive forms are treated differently in GSI course:
[Recipient] + [Action] or, if Agent is mentioned in the sentence:
[Recipient] + [Action] + [by Agent].

 - ❖ This is done for several reasons:
 - To further differentiate the roles of Agent and Recipient.
Agent can *be* something or *do* something, while Recipient can only experience effects;

 - To specifically sensitize you to passive forms and help you see them as one single chunk of information rather than a complex predicate.

 - ❖ This is important because “-ed” forms occur very frequently in a sentence. In addition to the Passive voice, they can mean a wide range of other things. For example:
 - “I am glad to have completed my report” (Form: Perfect infinitive, Active. Function: Object);

 - “I am glad to have been introduced to this person” (Form: Perfect infinitive, Passive. Function: Object);

 - “The number of submitted reports has increased” (Form: Participle, used as Adjective. Function: Modifier);

 - “The report was completed on time” (Form: Verb in the Passive voice. Function: Predicate).
-

Common roles of '-ing' words

❖ **Consider the following sentences:**

- Smoking kills.
- This was a highly satisfying experience.
- Check the availability of sizes before purchasing.

❖ In the first example, the '-ing' word tells you 'What is it?' It is smoking that kills.

❖ In the second case, it tells you 'What is it like?' The experience is satisfying.

❖ Whereas in the third instance, the '-ing' word denotes time.

In combinations with 'after'/'before'/'while' it says *when* something should happen.

Check availability before you do your purchase.

These are some of the very common roles of '-ing' words.

If you would like a more detailed review of how '-ing' words work, please see sections 293 – 300 *-ing forms* in *Practical English Usage* by Michael Swan (Third Edition).

Nominalization

❖ **This is when you make *a noun* from *a verb* or *an adjective*.**

❖ **To do so, you usually need a suffix like:**

-ness;

-ion;

-ment;

-ing.

E.g.: happy – happiness; reduce – reduction; manage – management; read – reading.

❖ **As you can see, many common words derive from nominalization. So why avoid it?**

- If you check the sources, they mainly discourage the *excessive* usage of ‘-ness’ and ‘-ion’, rather than rule it out altogether.
 - Some words (e.g. ‘-ing’ words) have other important roles, so less nominalization means less confusion.
-

Participles and Adjectives

❖ **Participles are ‘-ing’ and ‘-ed’ forms, except for the cases when ‘-ing’ form is used as a noun-like structure (= Gerund).**

❖ **In a sentence, ‘-ing’ and ‘-ed’ forms can take the** Verb

In this case they help to make tenses. *E.g.: has been doing; was asked; is going.*

❖ **They can also be used like adjectives, i.e. the words that describe the noun.**

In this case they take the slot of the Modifier: (what kind of)

○ You can use them as adjectives before nouns. *E.g.: a broken window.*

○ You can also use them after nouns. *E.g.: It is more useful to extend the range of tests done.*

❖ **You can use adjectives with the verb ‘to be’.**

E.g.: Various treatment options are available. For the sake of simplification, this course tells you that in such cases the adjective takes the slot of Object

Strictly speaking, it’s not. Academic grammar considers this to be a type of the predicate. However, the main focus of this course is a quick self-check. This is why the theory of the sentence is simplified here to a three-component structure. This simplification has its roots in the note-taking of interpreters.

❖ **If you do quick pattern recognition during the self-check,** chances are high that

Tense forms (both active and passive) vs *Participles* (before and after nouns) vs *Adjectives* (after the verb ‘to be’) can be a challenge. This is why:

- this course includes specific sensitization and disambiguation exercises;
- contains a presentation on disambiguating ‘-ing’ and ‘-ed’ in a sentence;
- provides downloadable flowcharts.

If you would like a more detailed review of participles, please see sections 408 – 411 in *Practical English Usage* by Michael Swan (Third Edition).

- ❖ **The basic form of the verb usually has the 'to' marker: to go, to walk, to read, etc. This form is called *the infinitive* (or, more precisely, *full infinitive* or *to-infinitive*). It does not talk about someone's actions, but simply denotes an idea in general: 'to read' is just an idea of reading, nobody is reading anything.**

- ❖ **However, there is also the so-called *bare infinitive*, i.e. the infinitive without 'to', that occurs in a number of situations:**
 - With modal verbs like *can* or *may*, e.g.: 'You may go'.
 - In *Object+infinitive constructions* after *see, hear, feel*, e.g.: 'I saw him come in'.
 - After *why* or *why not*, e.g.: 'Why not take a break?'

This one *is* about someone's actions.

- ❖ **You may also be thinking of various tense forms:**
 - Negation in the Present Simple, e.g.: 'This doesn't work'.
 - Statement in the Present Simple in plural, e.g.: 'Numbers show'.
 - Future Simple, e.g.: 'I will go'.

These forms are not infinitives, and they *do* denote someone's actions.

If you would like a more detailed review of infinitives, please see sections 279 – 292 in *Practical English Usage* by Michael Swan (Third Edition).

-
- ❖ **As you may remember from the previous section, *bare infinitive* is the infinitive without ‘to’. You can find it, among other:**
 - With modal verbs like *can* or *may*, e.g.: ‘You may go’.
 - In *Object+infinitive* constructions after the verbs of perception such as *see, hear, feel* in the active voice, e.g.: ‘I saw him come in’.

 - ❖ **However, if you use the verbs of perception in the passive voice, you will need the *full infinitive*: ‘He was seen to come in’; ‘They were heard to laugh’.**

 - ❖ **The same is true for the verbs of saying and thinking: ‘This problem is thought to be difficult’.**

 - ❖ **And lastly, the *full infinitive* can convey three important types of meaning in a sentence:**
 - *Purpose*, as in ‘I went to buy a book’ (what did I go for?).
 - *Additional information*, as in ‘I went to buy something to eat’ (what did I intend to buy?).
 - *Result*, as in ‘I found my computer only to discover it was not working’ (= I found *and* discovered that it was not working).

If you would like a more detailed review of infinitives with and without ‘to’, please see sections 242 and 418 in *Practical English Usage* by Michael Swan (Third Edition). The roles of infinitives in the sentence are described in sections 289 – 292.

Rules of good text

Compiled and adapted from
Plain English for Doctors and Other Medical Scientists
by David Daly, Gertrude A. Daly and Oscar Linares
and *English for Writing Research Papers*
by Adrian Wallwork

1. Don't replace key terms with synonyms.
2. Use 'vivid language':
 - 2.1. plain English vs abstract Latin words;
 - 2.2. shorter words;
 - 2.3. active voice;
 - 2.4. no nominalization;
 - 2.5. no noun strings.
3. Keep sentences around 10 – 20 words long;
a few sentences could be about 25 – 35 words long,
provided they are very clear.
4. Mind the number of objects that the verb takes and the
prepositions that it requires.
5. Make sure that the words convey the intended meaning.
6. Make sure that the subject and the verb are among the
first 4 – 5 words.
7. Don't split the subject and the verb with more than
2 – 3 words.

... plus something else (see Refreshers and Practice)

A few practical examples (from my former blog)

Teaching Finnish to Immigrants in Finland: Firsthand Account of a Language Professional

Is Finnish taught to immigrants properly?

In September 2022, YLE's *All Points North* podcast was covering the teaching of Finnish to immigrants in Finland. Apparently, the topic has sparked intense debate among the listeners. One of the listeners with a PhD in Educational Technology has put it quite strongly: Finns don't know how to teach Finnish, especially to speakers of English.

I am a certified teacher of English, I have experience teaching students at the university, and I have completed a few courses of Finnish in Finland, which has eventually led me to a B1 YKI testi.

I would frame my feedback about teaching language to immigrants a bit softer: it seems to be a bit old-school. I must emphasize, though, that I have observed a similar trend elsewhere, and looks like it is a common issue for language teaching in general. The practise on the ground seems to be in stark contrast with what is being taught to students of teaching professions. In my opinion, what makes it old-school is little or no regard for *metacognitive skills*.

What makes the teaching methods old-school?

Let me put it in context for you. Metacognition means knowing and understanding your thought processes. You can develop this skill in your students thus trying to elicit any difficulties during their learning and helping to identify the underlying causes. You can also develop this skill yourself, which will help you better control the efficacy of your work.

The practicalities of metacognition in teaching have long been addressed by a famous scholar from the University of Helsinki, Kirsti Lonka, the author of *Phenomenal Learning from Finland*. Her research is often being quoted, but does not seem to be implemented in practice. At least in teaching language to immigrants. Meanwhile, her studies of learner profiles (called *epistemic profiles*) give a clue to approaching varied groups of learners in a tailored fashion.

To put it simply, learners in the same classroom are at different stages of readiness to interact with teachers and acquire knowledge. Some people would just be gathering knowledge for the mere sake of it, others would be interested in practical applications, while someone else would be concerned with building a coherent scheme that would fully incorporate the newly acquired knowledge. These stages are in fact the three most common epistemic profiles called *fact-oriented profile*, *pragmatic profile* and *reflective-collaborative profile*, respectively.

A classroom is a mix of epistemic profiles

So a classroom is always a mix of epistemic profiles. While a fact-oriented learner would probably be fine with just listening to explanations about grammar and then doing any kind of exercise, their neighbour, a knowledge-builder, would need to know how the explanation fits into what s/he already knows. At the same time, a knowledge user in the same classroom would probably be unhappy about a grammar exercise unless s/he can clearly see the added value of doing it.

This is where metacognition comes in handy. It helps identify the essential emotional cues that learners display. For example, some of the important cues that I have observed among my peers included: blaming oneself for not being diligent, not knowing enough words, not being quick to learn, or even not being smart. What I realized was that my peers either thought these emotions to be typical for the learning process in general, or to be the manifestations of their personal flaws. Yet, all of these cues remained overlooked by teachers.

Why profiles remain overlooked?

I think my professional background has helped me recognize the common difficulties in the classroom and speculate on the underlying causes of ignoring the epistemic profiles.

First, groups of immigrant learners are usually large, and there is probably no time to keep track of 30 individuals all the time. Because epistemic profiles are not static, they are subject to change during the training. Tracking them *does* take effort. Teaching staff is likely short of time.

Second, I assume that there is fear of getting lost. If you were to give 30 individual pieces of advice / keep track of 30 ever-evolving learning pathways, you would probably conclude that there is no way to make your lessons focused anymore.

Third, 'epistemic profiles' and 'emotions' probably sounds more like psychology. I guess there is certain reluctance to deal with cross-disciplinary domains. I assume that this mindset could be summarized this way: 'I did not hear that during my learning, so it doesn't exist / has no relevance to me / not my job, why should I care?' An alternative scenario would be the opposite. Educators (teachers, curriculum designers, administrators, etc.) probably *have* observed the variability of epistemic profiles in practice, as well as the related emotional burden. Yet, they probably think this to be an intrinsic property of learning anyway (or, at worst, they are just so burned out that they just let things go).

In either case, an implicit inference starts hanging in the air: 'learning is doomed to be boring, painful and inefficient anyway'. I think I have observed signs of this mindset among some practitioners, which inevitably translated to their learners. 'Ok, I just have to tolerate', a learner would think to themselves, 'because I got caught up here, I need to do this anyway. No pains, no gains. Apparently, the intrinsic pain is this. The intrinsic result is poor. It all is designed to be like this'. What learners eventually come up with, if asked, is unspecific feedback about the teaching being 'bad', 'unsatisfactory', or 'unprofessional'. While some of these feelings are related to other issues truly outside of the immediate domain of schools (work, social security, finances, etc.), there is still a great deal of what can be relieved through optimized approaches to teaching.

'Too much, too busy, too complicated, and therefore not feasible and none of my business'. What can be done?

During my time as instructor in Conference Interpreting, I organized quite a few one-day workshops for ad hoc groups of learners (i.e. *brush up* or *core review* events). This is where the difference in epistemic profiles is at its strongest. One biggest takeaway from these events would be *communication*. At any point in time, every learner should understand, what the sense of their stay in the room is. It reminds me of multiplayer computer games in which players can perform different tasks, but they always have a HUD (head-up display) in front of them, and can reference themselves to the bigger picture. In my experience, one very efficient way to set up this mapping / monitoring is through sliders or radar charts.

One might object that there is curriculum in place. There is one teacher per classroom, and group events cannot be individualized to fit all the needs of every single learner at the same time. True. But charts and sliders can.

Come up with a simple classification of things that you are teaching. Then come up with a simple rating, let's say from 0 to 4. This will give you the necessary focus. What end result do you want your students to achieve? What results do they realistically achieve? Frame it in terms of your simple classification and rating. What does the average student profile look like? What is the profile like at the start of the studies? Do your lessons sufficiently cover all of this classification? What would be three most common learner pathways in terms of your classification? What is the value of your teaching instruments in bringing skills from one stage to another? Actually, *do* you have enough instruments to help learners go down the common pathways in the first place?

Learn from CELTA and assign emotional values

No secret, language is about different skills and components. The classics of CELTA is *Skills* and *Systems*. Skills can be receptive (Reading and Listening) or productive (Writing and Speaking), while systems encompass *Phonology*, *Grammar*, *Vocabulary* and *Functional* language. Assessments in exams are built around these criteria. Lesson planning is built around these Skills and Systems. **And I guess you know that they cost different effort to learners: i.e. learning 10 new words is probably easier and more straightforward than learning a tricky grammar rule.** You have probably also noticed that everyone, including yourself, has their favourite components. E.g. at school, I hated writing and doing grammar exercises but I loved speaking and using new words in large blocks, such as sentences or useful phrases. In other words, not only do skills and systems cost variable amount of effort, but also they create different emotional burden. This is my point: assign different values in terms of emotions and effort to the components of your classification. Clearly, there will be different costs for different learners. Furthermore, they will evolve over time with the same learner. *These combinations are many but not endless*. Eventually, all of them will be down to a few broad groups, such as the epistemic profiles by Kirsti Lonka.

Virheellinen Sliders

I built [a prototype to explore such combinations](#). It will help to bring teachers and students on the same page. The tool can be used in a variety of ways. Students can map their skills and explain their pain points in teacher-understandable terms. Teachers can get a better idea of where the learner is and what to advise. This tool will work well in large environments where personal contact is difficult to build, such as language courses for immigrants.

As the name suggests, the app is a panel of five different criteria, graded on a scale of 0 to 4. There is a concise explanation of each criterion and a summary of the skill profiles. The number of all mathematically possible combinations is 3125, and they can be gathered into roughly 77 groups. Looks like these groups cover many, if not all, important points on a pathway from 0 to B1 of all types of learners. While building this app, I relied on the CEFR specifications as well as my own professional experience and empirical observations.

Virheellinen Sliders are currently intended for information purposes solely, and the app will definitely benefit from user feedback. As this is the first iteration, there may be inaccuracies and errors, although I took reasonable precautions to avoid these. With modern technologies, it took me little time to create, and I believe a collective effort may give rise to a similar, more precise and more validated (or perhaps user / school-specific) tool.

Subject-specific lessons for A2 level learners

I've recently had a useful and practice-oriented conversation with one of the subject teachers. It addressed a very relevant topic: how to ensure positive user experience and level-appropriate delivery of short-term subject courses (or, rather, subject modules) for learners, whose level of a foreign language may be somewhere around A2.

Although the topic is not quite new (and requires a lot of consideration indeed), some recent technological developments could give it greater momentum. There are a lot of techniques in interpreter training, as well as professional tips and tricks, from which language teaching could greatly benefit. Interestingly, while interpreting/translation actively borrows useful approaches from language teaching (such as the analogue of A-B-C levels of mastery, *see Competence levels in translation: working towards a European framework by PACTE Group*), language teaching seems to be surprisingly reluctant to adapt and adopt, and often seems to be reinventing the wheels, bikes, and all conceivable sorts of other things.

Let us take an example. You are about to organize a short course on a very specific topic, such as hygiene, household management, first aid or a similar one. Your goal is to deliver it to a group of learners, whose level of language is known to be A2 – B1 at best.

By definition (e.g. see A2 level descriptors at COE website), the A2 level is meant to be limited to a number of familiar situations. The range and scope of these situations is determined by CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) and specifications, if they exist for a given language (e.g. see Threshold 1990 (CUP) Specifications at EALTA website). It is usually limited to the well-known subjects, such as travelling, friends, meals, free-time, etc.

What you actually do when you embark upon a few-day-long subject course is somewhat diverge from CEFR and make the new subject field familiar for your learners. I mean, you should literally familiarize the learners with the new *Words, Slots, Connections, Combinations* and *Patterns* that are specific for the new topic. Interpreters know it all too well.

After you have agreed to interpret at an event and before you walk into the booth on day one of a conference / expert meeting / workshop, the preparation phase takes place. This phase would seem to contribute to your professional performance most of all. This is exactly the time when interpreters create glossaries of words, lists of typical verbs and typical Verb + Noun, Noun + Adjective, and Verb + Adverb combinations. It is at this time that they pick up some elements of professional jargon, jokes, sayings, etc. In other words, they do their best to sound natural in the audience of the subject matter experts.

Before the arrival of the technological advances of the recent years, it was probably the hardest part of the preparation routines. And this is why any sort of a glossary or notes were worth their weight in gold. Yes, someone had to collect it all manually, and this is why the preparation was difficult.

For the same reason, level-appropriate textbooks were the only realistic means of teaching a bit of subject-specific topics to A2 learners. For the same reason, pre-reading (or pre-lesson) exercises were so painful to prepare from scratch.

However, with some common tools (such as Sketch Engine, DtSearch, DeepL, etc.), it has literally become a matter of seconds, maybe 2 minutes maximum. The workflow from texts to Quizlets has never been quicker, has never contributed better to teacher's confidence and learner's convenience.

Based on my empirical observations, what makes new materials painful for learners is the constantly interrupted sense of flow (e.g. see the concept of flow in psychology, developed by M. Csikszentmihályi).

Everyone seems to recognize that a bit of unfamiliar words, guess work and, of course, the related discomfort is generally OK. However, no one seems to specifically consider, how much is too much.

I admit that I didn't have time to look into the most recent scientific publications, but based on my observations and personal communication, I would say that this number stands at 10 – 15%. The imminent need to guess every other word (which could be case with the A2 learners on subject specific modules) likely causes a huge sense of discomfort, frustration, or reluctance. A useful approach would seem to be group-oriented and material-specific preparation.

1. The person in charge, for example, the teacher or the teaching assistant, extracts words and word combinations from the texts that they are planning to distribute. This could be done, for example, with Sketch Engine, WordClouds, DtSearch or similar tools.
2. The list of the extracted items is reduced to a reasonable amount, such as 80 – 100 words. The teacher and / or the assistant can then choose the words that are 100% new to the group, topic-specific words, or the familiar words. The latter option would help to show the learners that the words they already know are indeed versatile (see *Patterns*).
3. The CELTA-recommended number of new words per a Vocabulary lesson is ten. Maybe twenty. So before the subject-specific course you either have to arrange five ($5 \times 20 = 100$) intense Vocabulary lessons (check lesson shapes in CELTA), or organize an interpreter-training-like workshop. This would not be a traditional lesson shape, but definitely a helpful one. Interpreters do not necessarily remember the 100 – 200 new words before each meeting on a new topic. They usually start to properly remember them by day 2 or 3 of the conference.

How do you cope on day one? Well, you simply keep a glossary in front of you. Some people prefer to print the five or six A4 pages and highlight the most used terms, as well as take additional notes throughout the conference. This is the alternative approach that could help you keep it quick and efficient.

Let learners familiarize themselves with Quizlets and try a few tests in the forgiving multiple choice mode. Let them print out the glossary and highlight the words, patterns, and combinations that they hear throughout the course.

Some examples of the pre-lesson activities are available [here](#) and [here](#). In this case, the aids are related to Food Safety. If learners work with these aids before the relevant lessons, I think they will report very positive experiences.

A Conversation with a Talented Learner

Correct me if I'm wrong, but I think one age-old preconception about learning languages is still alive. A surprisingly large number of people would still seem to think that learning a foreign language is intrinsically hard and unrewarding, which makes it comparable to a steam engine with only 10% efficiency.

I think I can still sense this attitude among many people, learners and teachers alike, in different parts of the world.

I've recently met a successful learner who seemed to confirm these observations. She mastered her foreign language to the level of full working proficiency, and one would have never thought that she once struggled with her learning.

Hers seems to be a very familiar story. At some point in time, she felt stuck with her learning. As she put it, the words she knew simply did not piece together into anything meaningful.

If it weren't for her natural talent and creativity, she would almost certainly be having the blues. However, she was able to intuitively find a workable and efficient solution. She started to look for bits of authentic texts that seemed to convey her intended meaning and then learn and use these bits in her own speech. Looks self-evident? Yet, it was not trivial or straightforward for the learner. It took someone who is not a language professional a lot of creativity and enthusiasm to explore the feasible options before she finally came up with the workable option.

Interestingly, **the approach to learning that she discovered has been long known in interpreter training.** It is also known in academic writing. Just one compelling example would be the *Academic Phrasebank* by prof. John Morley. At the same time, some existing classifications of language mastery seem to attribute the learning of stock phrases to the lower levels solely. An example would be the *memorized proficiency* or *zero plus* level. It is used to describe the mastery level at which learners only have memorized knowledge of stock phrases, such as short facts about themselves. While not aiming to criticize the classification itself, I simply would like to highlight that it probably reflects the deep-rooted and the well-established preconception that I mentioned at the beginning.

Now, let me ask you a question. Do learners actually have to reinvent the existing solutions? Is it not us, the teaching community, that should offer guidance? If a specific approach were to originate from a different professional domain, such as interpreter training or academic writing, should language teachers immediately reject it, just because 'interpreting' sounds more complicated than 'teaching at A2/B1 level'? Are we not looking for learner-oriented, demand-driven and multidisciplinary solutions? If so, why should we still be relying on the enduring stereotypes about the practical language teaching?

Would it be common for language learners to feel reluctant about attending their next lesson? Do they ever struggle with the desire to leave the room midway through their day? If yes, is it because learning is doomed to be hard, unrewarding and inefficient by design? Or, worse, would someone think that it is because learners are commonly not quite willing to use any effort?

My observations would seem to suggest that by default learners in the same classroom are at different stages of readiness to interact with teachers. These stages are called *epistemic profiles*. In one of her publications, prof. Kirsti Lonka from the University of Helsinki described three very common ones: the stage at which a person is focused on gathering knowledge (fact-oriented profile), on building it (reflective-

collaborative profile), and on using it (pragmatic profile). Although they are called profiles, they are not once-and-for-lifetime characteristics of individuals. They tend to vary with time, and learners may fit different profiles at different periods of their training.

This is my point. A classroom is always a mix of different epistemic profiles. While a fact-oriented learner would probably be fine with just listening the explanations about grammar and then doing any kind of exercise, their neighbour, a knowledge builder, will need to know how this explanation fits into what s/he already knows. At the same time, a knowledge user in the same classroom will probably struggle with the grammar exercise, unless they see the clear added value of doing it.

I organized quite a few one-day workshops in interpreting for ad hoc groups of learners (brush up or core review events). This is where the difference in epistemic profiles is at its strongest. One biggest takeaway from these events would be *Communication*. At any point in time, every learner should understand, what the sense of their stay in the room is. It reminds me of multiplayer computer games in which players can perform different tasks, but they always have a HUD (head-up display) in front of them, and can reference themselves to the bigger picture. In my experience, one very efficient way to set up this mapping/monitoring in the classroom is through sliders or radar charts.

I know, there is a curriculum in place. There is one teacher per classroom, and group events cannot be individualized to fit all the needs of every single learner at the same time. But charts and sliders can.

Come up with a simple classification of things that you are teaching. Then come up with a simple rating, let's say from 0 to 4 or 5. This will give you the necessary focus.

- What end result do you want your students to achieve?
- What results do they realistically achieve?
- What does the average student profile look like?
- What is the profile like at the start of the studies?
- Do your lessons sufficiently cover all of this classification?
- What would be three most common learner pathways in terms of your classification?
- What is the value of your teaching instruments in bringing skills from one stage to another?
- Actually, do you have enough instruments to help learners go down the common pathways in the first place?

Frame answers in terms of your simple classification and rating. Tell your students about your framework. Tell them about their pathways. Tell them about your instruments. Set realistic expectations. For example, with fewer than 600 words, a learner probably feels tongue-tied. Will 2000 words make them feel any better? There is a long way from 600 to 2000 words. Will you encourage your learners to take this effort because this will help them feel better?

My point is: **no**. It is not 2000 words that make a difference, but the combinations of words. Even if you know just 700 words but these are naturally occurring pairs, such as *Verb + Noun* or *Noun + Adjective* (a method for learning words known as *lexical neighbours*), you will feel much better than someone who knows 2000 random words.

This is what I mean by setting expectations based on your classification. Thus, if 2500 is the top of my classification, and it is rated at 4, I can still say to my students that having a 2 on the 'Words' scale is still fine, as long as your 'Combinations' are at 1 or above. If my student is tired of learning words, I can probably let them go ahead with something else that they choose, but both of us will monitor their profile to keep it balanced. This way, I will avoid pushing for a specific task at any cost. And this is where the learning-related emotions probably start.